

An oenological approach to increase the consumer acceptability of black chokeberry (*Aronia melanocarpa* L.) juice

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Abstract

The black chokeberry (*Aronia melanocarpa* L.) is a berry with exceptionally high concentrations of phenolic compounds with high antioxidative potential as well as high amounts of minerals, trace elements and vitamins. The health beneficial effect of aronia consumption was shown in several studies. Recently, these properties have made aronia a new domestic and, thus, sustainable 'superfood'. However, in contrast to other products aronia juice lacks pronounced fruitiness, but shows distinct bitterness and astringency. These sensory properties are the limiting factors for a high consumer acceptability of aronia juice. In this study, we investigated the applicability of fining technologies to aronia juice with the aim to reduce the astringency and bitterness. Commercially available fining agents that are well established in wine technology were selected for these experiments. The effect of these measures was investigated by (i) HS SPME GC-MS to investigate the impact on volatile compounds, (ii) and UV-Vis spectrophotometry to follow the colour changes upon fining (iii) sensory analysis to evaluate the bitterness and astringency. Fining of aronia juice leads to a significant change in the aronia volatilome and a reduction of the monomeric polyphenols. Hence, fining results in changes on odour- as well as taste-active compounds and causes multimodal changes in the sensory perception.

Keywords: black chokeberry juice, fining, volatiles, bitterness, astringency

Introduction

The black chokeberry (*Aronia melanocarpa* L.) has gained increasing popularity during the last years as a domestic 'superfood'. The cultivation areas have been continuously enlarged in Austria. The berry is well known due to its exceptionally high content of polyphenolic substances (i.e., anthocyanins, pro-anthocyanidins, flavonols and phenolic acids) with the highest content of total phenolics compared to most other berry species [1]. The consumption of polyphenolic compounds is assumed to have beneficial health effects. Their antioxidative potential, anti-cancer, cardioprotective, and anti-diabetic effects as well as other advantages were subject of many investigations [2-4, 6-7].

In contrast to other products, aronia juice is lacking pronounced fruitiness, but shows distinct bitterness and astringency which is a major limitation for its consumption for most consumers [5]. Due to the young history of chokeberry juice, only little research has been performed with the aim to reduce its bitterness and astringency. However, there is vast knowledge and experience from oenology on how to cope with bitterness and astringency in red wines. Fining is a well-established technological measure in winemaking, which is used to reduce astringency and bitterness by removing polyphenols and tannins. Therefore, in this study we investigated the effects of fining on not-from-concentrate chokeberry juice. Six different commercially available fining agents were applied on chokeberry juices. The effects were evaluated using (i) headspace SPME-GC-MS to investigate the impact on aronia volatiles, (ii) UV-Vis spectrophotometric methods to investigate the impact on the colour of the juices and (iii) sensory methods to investigate the impact of fining on the overall flavour with a focus on bitterness and astringency.

Experimental

Material

Not-from-concentrate chokeberry juice was prepared from approximately 400 kg fully ripe aronia berries that were harvested in the South of Austria (variety Nero, harvest year 2019). The berries were processed by a local fruit processing company immediately after the harvest. The pasteurized juices were stored in the dark at 5°C in 3 L polyethylene bags until further use. Fining was performed with six different commercially available fining agents (A - Degustin, B - ErbiGel Bio, C - Erbslöh Mostgelatine, D - Vinpur Special, E - LittoFresh Liquid, F - ErbiGel Liquid; all provided by Erbslöh Austria GmbH). The fining agents were applied in the highest dosage recommended for the fining of red wine and let react over night at 4°C. After coagulation took place, filtration or decantation was used to separate the clear juice from the precipitate.

Gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS) analysis of the volatile compounds

An aliquot of 100 μL of chokeberry juice (untreated or fined juices) was transferred into 20 mL headspace vials with the addition of 50 mg NaCl. 2-Octanol was added as an internal standard (100 ng absolute). The extraction/enrichment of the volatiles was performed by headspace solid-phase-microextraction (HS-SPME; 2 cm stable flex fibre, 50/30 μm DVB/Car/PDMS fibre) for 20 minutes at 40°C. Samples were stirred thoroughly during the enrichment process. The GC-MS analysis was conducted on a non-polar column (Shimadzu GC-2010 Plus, MS QP 2020, Shimadzu Europa GmbH; Rxi-5ms 30 m \times 0.25 mm \times 1 μm , Restek Corporation, USA; EI 70 eV, scan range 35 - 350 amu). The samples were analysed in triplicate in randomized order. The identification of the volatiles was based on probability-based matching of their mass spectra with those from MS libraries, authentic reference compounds and linear temperature-programmed retention indices. Retention indices were calculated by measuring the homologous series of *n*-alkanes (C5-C26) using the same GC-MS conditions as for the samples. Data deconvolution and integration was done with the PARADISE software, based on the PARAFAC2 model [8]. Semi-quantification was done via the internal standard (2-octanol) assuming a response factor of 1 for all compounds.

Monomeric index

The determination of the monomeric index was performed according to Bonerz et al., 2006 [9]. The monomeric index was calculated as the ratio of the absorption of the monomeric and polymeric anthocyanins ($A_{\text{mono}}/A_{\text{poly}}$) at $\lambda=520$ nm after discolouration of the monomeric anthocyanins upon a reaction with $\text{K}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_5$.

Sensory evaluation

Sensory evaluation of the juices was performed with a well-trained expert panel, experienced in analysing chokeberry products (14 members) under standardized conditions in the sensory laboratory. Descriptive analysis as well as discrimination tests were applied. Sensory data were recorded using Compusense sensory software (Compusense Inc., Guelph, Canada).

Statistical evaluation of the results

Statistical analysis was performed using one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) to identify statistically significant differences between the samples as well as principal component analysis (PCA), using Pearson correlation to find correlations between volatiles and samples. For statistical analysis, the MS excel add-in XLSTAT was used (Addinsoft 2020, Long Island, NY, USA).

Results and discussion

In this study, we evaluated the impact of fining on not-from-concentrate aronia juice with the aim to reduce the pronounced astringency and bitterness of the products. It is well known from oenology, that fining does not only impact the concentrations of phenolic compounds of the product. Depending on the selected fining agent, interaction with volatile compounds may be observed and may, thus, lead to alterations of the overall flavour of the product. As a consequence, we investigated aronia volatiles, the overall flavour of the juices as well as the so-called monomeric index as a measure for anthocyanins as a major group of phenolic compounds in chokeberry juice.

Headspace SPME-GC-MS was used to analyse the volatile compounds of aronia juice. A total of 74 volatile compounds could be identified in the aronia juice. As reported in a previous study [5], in contrast to other fruit juice types, only very few fruit esters are present in aronia juice; on the other hand, we identified a long list of alcohols, aldehydes and ketones, some free short-chain fatty acids as well as some terpenes and terpenoids. The results from HS-SPME-GC-MS analysis showed a significant reduction of many volatiles upon the fining process. Mainly low-molecular weight esters and ketones, which are generally made responsible for fruitiness, were significantly decreased in their concentrations. Terpenes were hardly affected by the fining process; free fatty acids did not show a clear trend, neither did alcohols. To better visualize the effect of fining on the volatiles of aronia juice, we performed multivariate data analysis in terms of principal component analysis.

Figure 1 gives the biplot showing the correlations of aronia volatiles and the juices treated with different fining agents in comparison to the non-treated juice. The effect of fining on the aronia volatiles can be seen clearly. The untreated juice is the only product located in quadrant IV and shows a high correlation with a large number of volatiles, specifically with esters, some alcohols and ketones. The biplot also demonstrates the different interactions of the selected fining agents with volatile compounds. Whereas the juice fined with the fining agent A is centred in quadrant I and highly correlates with a high number of C6 'green leave' aldehydes and alcohols, the juices fined with fining agents B and C are located at the border of quadrant I and II and only correlate with few compounds from different compound classes. On the contrary, juices treated with the fining agents D, E and

F show high correlations to one another; interestingly, high correlations were observed with the 2- and 3-methyl-branched butanoic acids. Having in mind the rather unpleasant sensory properties and the low odour threshold values of these acids, this finding might be an indication for a negative impact of the fining procedure on the flavour of the juices.

Figure 1: Biplot of the PCA analysis (Pearson correlation) of the volatile compounds of the untreated aronia juice B in comparison to juices that were fined with commercially available fining agents (BsA Degustin, BsB ErbiGel Bio, BsC Erbslöh Mostgelatine, BsD Vinpur Special, BsE LittoFresh Liquid, BsF ErbiGel Liquid).

Phenolic compounds that are present in high concentrations in aronia juice are made responsible for the bitterness and the pronounced astringency of the products. Thus, in addition to the analysis of the volatile compounds, we followed the fining process by analysing the so-called monomeric index as a measure of the total content of anthocyanins in the juice. This was done to evaluate if the use of fining agents designed for oenological practices might also work for the treatment of aronia juice. The results of the fining experiments with respect to the monomeric index are given in Table 1. Fining with four out of six fining agents resulted in a low, however, significant decrease of the monomeric index as a result of the fining process. These results – in combination with the formation of a highly coloured precipitate – show that the selected fining agents interact and reduce the phenolic components of aronia juice. The decrease in the monomeric index indicates a stronger reduction of monomeric phenolic compounds (i.e., anthocyanins) in comparison to the polymeric phenols.

Preliminary results from sensory evaluation demonstrate a change in the sensory properties of the fined juices in comparison to the unfined reference juice. Results from descriptive analysis demonstrate that bitterness was reduced by almost all fining agents, whereas the perceived astringency remained unchanged upon fining with fining agents A and C, for example, while fining agent D also reduced astringency. It is also worthwhile to note that the reduction of bitterness and/or astringency led to an overall change of the perceived flavour; fining with fining agent A led to a reduced perception of bitterness with a simultaneous increase in perceived fruitiness, while fining with fining agent F led to an increase in the perceived astringency and sourness. Monomeric flavon-3-ols as well as dimers and trimers are described to be bitter, but not astringent [10]. Thus, the reduced bitterness-intensity indicates a reduction of monomeric anthocyanins upon the fining process, rather than a reduction of the condensed polyphenols.

These findings correlate well with the values for the monomeric index that also show a reduction of monomeric polyphenols due to the fining process. These preliminary results from sensory evaluation combined with the results obtained from GC-MS analysis of the aronia volatilome and colour measurements indicate, that complex interactions take place between the juice and the respective fining agent leading to multimodal sensory effects that are specific for each fining agent.

Table 1: Monomeric index of the unfined and fined juices (n=3).

Sample	Monomer index	Sig [§]
Unfined juice	12,60 ± 1,1	-
Fined juice (Degustin)	11,52 ± 0,7	ns
Fined juice (ErbiGel Bio)	10,17 ± 0,5	*
Fined juice (Erbslöh Mostgelatine)	13,55 ± 1,9	ns
Fined juice (Vinpur Special)	11,39 ± 0,2	*
Fined juice (LittoFresh Liquid)	11,04 ± 0,9	*
Fined juice (ErbiGel Liquid)	10,78 ± 0,6	*

[§]significance of difference between the unfined juice and the fined juices FJ
 ns = no significant difference between means (p > 0.05); * significant at the 5% level

Conclusion

The results of this study show that fining of aronia juice might be a suitable oenological practice to specifically reduce its pronounced bitterness. The findings from the analysis of the aronia volatilome, UV-Vis spectrophotometry on polyphenols and the sensory evaluation indicate that different fining agents do not interact in a uniform way with the juice components. This specific behaviour results in different multimodal effects on the sensory perception of the fined product. The preliminary results from this study may serve as a good basis for further investigations to identify the most appropriate fining agent and its optimum dosage for the specific composition of aronia juice. With this and the follow-up experiments, we hope to successfully contribute to improve the sensory properties of this highly valuable domestic product and to increase the consumer acceptability of aronia juice.

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